

**A STUDY ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS PROBLEMS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS
OF SRI. MALAPRABHA COOPERATIVE SUGAR INDUSTRIES IN BELGAUM
DISTRICT OF KARNATAKA STATE**

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ABSTRACT

Sugar industry is one of the major agro-based industries found in M. K. Hubballi, Belagavi district, Karnataka state. We know that the consumption of sugar in daily life is increasing and the demand for sugar in the markets is also increasing. This research paper attempts to examine the problems and prospects of the sugar industry in M. K. Hubballi, Belagavi district, Karnataka state. This research paper is mainly based on the data collected from well-known published secondary sources. This research paper includes a critical study on some of the serious problems of the sugar industry in M. K. Hubballi, Belagavi district, Karnataka state and the prospects for the next generation.

Key words: Problems and Future Prospects, Sri. Malaprabha Cooperative Sugar Industries.

INTRODUCTION

M. K. Hubballi is the most important agro-based industry and a major industrial centre of the economy in the Belagavi district of the state of Karnataka. Major agricultural activities include cultivation of food grains, sugarcane, cotton, tobacco and oilseeds. The district also has agro-based industries such as sugar and jaggery production, milk processing and sericulture. Apart from this, Belagavi is a trading centre for these farmers. Sri Malaprabha Cooperative Sugar Factory Limited, M K Hubballi, is one of the pioneers in the cooperative sugar industries in the state of Karnataka, situated between the cities of Belgaum and Dharwad. The idea of setting up a sugar factory in the cooperative zone first came to the mind of the main promoter of this factory, Late Sri Mallappa Hosmani of Khanapur. Malaprabha Cooperative Sugar Factory is one of the largest and oldest sugar factories in North Karnataka.

It is located next to NH-4, making it the hub for all the raw materials available around the factory. Being located on the banks of Malaprabha river, it gets ample water. The location for the factory was first selected within the boundaries of Kyarakoppa village near Itagi. The Government of India finally selected and approved 110 acres of land at Kavalikumpi near Dastikoppa village. The factory initially started crushing at a rate of 1250 TCD, which was a large capacity then. However, with the passage of time, the supply of sugarcane increased. Therefore, to meet the required demand, the factory subsequently undertook expansions and it increased to 3500 TCD per day. The factory has ISS grade sugar manufacturing standards.

HISTORY/OVERVIEW

Sugarcane, the primary source of sugar, has been cultivated in Indian soil for centuries. Ancient Indian texts such as the Atharva Veda mention sugarcane, indicating its importance even in early times. Sugarcane cultivation became more widespread during the Mughal era, especially in the states of what is now Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. This period saw the rise of sugar in various dishes, further entrenching it in our culinary traditions. The British rule brought technological changes and new farming methods, laying the foundation for the sugar industry we see today. They established mills and factories in areas suitable for sugarcane cultivation. After India gained independence, the government saw the importance of sugar to the rural economy. This led to support in the form of policies, price controls and research institutes to help the industry grow. In states like Maharashtra, cooperative sugar factories became popular, giving farmers greater involvement in the industry. A brief history of the establishment of the factory is provided before analyzing the various advantages that led to the location of this factory at its present premises in the sugar district of Belgaum. (Fig No.1.1)

THE ENVIRONS OF SHRI MALAPRABHA SUGAR FACTORY M.K. HUBLI

I. Shri Malaprabha Sugar Factory Limited was registered in the year 1961. However, due to many factors including the collection of share capital the factory started its production on 22-1-1971 with 1250 TCD of sugarcane Production in the initial stages was carried on with monetary losses. However, since 1982-83 the factory started earning profits when its production reached 3500 MT per year.

II. The factory produces sugar and by-products such as bagasse, molasses, filter cake and it generates electricity through bagasse

III. The factory is situated near M. K. Hubli where facilities like transport water Labour electricity etc are available. The factory has total number of 17637 members of which 16632 are 'A' class members 808 are 'B' class members and 196 'C' class members. The Sugar Location of SMSSK Ltd, is M. K. Hubli.

SUGARCANE CRUSHING, DURATION AND PRODUCTION OF SUGAR

Details of the sugarcane crushed and the duration of crushing etc at the Malaprabha Sugar Factory M.K. Hubli. The following table provides the details of the sugarcane crushing of the Malaprabha Sugar factory at M.K. Hubli. (Table No.1.2)

Table No.1.3

Sugarcane crushing, Duration and production of sugar

Details	Year		
	2019-20	2021-22	2023-24
Date of Starting the crushing	17-11-05	03-11-06	26-11-07
Date of closing of the crushing	30-03 -06	25-0 5-07	23 -05 -0 8
Total working Days	134	205	181
Quantity of sugarcane crushed	369775 MT	621801 MT	557472 MT
Quantity of sugar produced	10335 MT	645640 MT	607425 MT
Yield percentage	10.98	10.30	10.80

Source: Agricultural Department M.S.S.K. Ltd., M.K. Hubli

The details in the above table indicate a steep rise in the total number of working days from 134 in 2019-20 to 2005 in 2021-22. However a decline in the number of working days to 181 in 2023-24 is noticed. The above trend is in consonance with the quantity of sugarcane crushed during the corresponding period.

The total quantity of sugar cane crushed rose from 369725 MT in 2019-20 to 621801 MT in 2021-22. However, the quantity of sugarcane crushed declined to 607425 MT in 2023-24. Fluctuations in the supply of sugarcane has resulted in the lower quantity of sugarcane crushed.

The total quantity of sugar produced by Malaprabha Sugar Factory in 2005 - 06 rose steeply from 10335 MT to 645640 MT in 2021-22. There has been a small decline in the production of sugar to 607425 MT in 2007 - 08.

The percentage of yield during the three-year period has been largely stable at 10.98% in 2005 - 06, 10.30% in 2021-22 and 10.80% in 2023-24.

CRUSHING SEASON 2008 - 09 DETAILS OF PERFORMANCE

The current year crushing season started on 10-11-2023. The adjoining table provides details regarding the following aspects.

- ❖ Crushing capacity
- ❖ Area preserved for the factory
- ❖ Quantity of cane available for crushing
- ❖ Rate given to farmers
- ❖ No of villages allotted

The details in the table provide some useful information about the location advantages of the Malaprabha Co-Operative Sugar Factory in terms of the raw material (Sugar Cane) availability position during the current year. The details further strengthen the locational advantages of the factory at its present premises particularly in relation to the assured supply of the sugar cane which is the main raw material for the manufacturing of sugar. (Table No.1.4).

Table No: 1.4

Crushing Season 2023-2024- Details of Performance Statement showing the details of the crushing season 2008-09

Name of the sugar Factory	Cane Crushing capacity in T.C. D	Date of commence of season	No. of villages allotted taluka wise 342 Total BLH - 117 BGM -90 SAVA-88 KHNP-47			Quantity of cane available for crushing in M. Ts	Total Quantity of sugar cane produced from other states			Whether permit is taken from DC to lift the sugar cane from Temporarily allocated area		Rate given to farmers per MT	
			Reserved Area	Temporarily reserved	Total		Member	Non-Member	Out of area	Total	Maharashtra		
2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Shri. Malaprabha Sahakari Sakkare Karkhane N) MK Hubli	3500 TCD	10-11-08	16,600 Acres	-	16,600 Acres	1)Previously submitted 500000 MT 2) Present situation 300.000 MT	3.50.00 MT 3.32.00 MT	-	8.50.0 00 MT 3.32.0 00 MT	Nil	Nil	Nil	Rs. 1300.00 + HRT Expenses

Source: Office of the M.S.S.K. M. K. Hubli -2008

Note: - cane availability for the season 2008 - 09 was 8,50,000 MT which is come down to 3,32,000 MT because of excessive diversion to Karnataka and Maharashtra states.

The factory is allotted total number of 342 villages for the supply of raw materials. The taluka wise allotment of sugarcane producing villages is provided in the following table.

(Table No1.5.)

Table No.1.5	
Taluka Wise Allotment of Sugar Cane Supplying Villages	
Taluka	No. of Villages
Bailhongal	117
Belgaum	90
Soundatti	88
Khanapur	47
Total	342

Source: Agricultural Department M.S.S.K.Ltd. M.K. Hubli

The total reserved area of sugarcane supply is 16.600 Acres. The Malaprabha Co-operative Sugarcane Factory has on installed cane crushing capacity of 3.500 TCD.

The quantity of cane available for crushing during the current year was 5.00.000 MT but due to diversion to other area the available cane supply has come down to 3.32.000.

SUGAR CANE PRICE - RATE GIVEN TO FARMERS PER M.T

The Malaprabha Co-operative Sugar Factory at MK Hubli has been given good price upward revsing continuously from 2002-03 to 2019-20 and a small decrease in the next two years However, there has been a maximum upward revision during 2008-09. The following table provides the details (Table No.1.6.)

Table No 1.6

Price of Sugar Cane offered to Farmers by the Factor

Year	Rate (Rs per MT)
2002-03	600 - 00
2003-04	800 - 00
2004-05	1000 - 00
2019-20	1200-00
2021-22	800 - 00
2023-24	900 - 00
2008-09	1300 - 00

Source: Agricultural Department M.S.S.K. Ltd. M.K.Hubli

The price of sugar cane offered to the sugarcane growing farmers have been upward revised continuously since the year 2002 - 03 when the price offered was Rs 600 per MT plus cost of harvesting and transport. The upward revised rate of buying sugarcane went up to Rs, 800/- per metric tonne in 2003 - 04 Rs 1000/- per metric ton in 2004-05 and further to Rs 1200/- per metric tonne in 2019-20 However, decline in sugarcane price to Rs 800 was observed in 2021-22. The price of sugar cane was revised upwards to Rs 900/- per metric tonne in 2023-24. The rate offered to farmers on their sugarcane in 2008- 09 was the highest at Rs 13.000 per metric tonne.

The above analysis indicates that the factory has been quite encouraging to the member farmers by way of offering price incentives and assure itself adequate raw material (Sugarcane) for its operations. With assured areas of sugarcane growing and assured supply of the same the choice of the location is quite appropriate from the point of view of raw material supply which happens to be the major consideration in the choice of location of an industry.

PROBLEMS OF M K HUBLI DISTRICT BELGAUM SUGAR INDUSTRY

1. Environmental problems

Many natural problems affect the success full growth of sugarcane in the district. They are.

- a) District get seasonal rainfalls i. e any for 3.5 months. But sugarcane is a long duration crop and needs well distributed rain. Rivers are seasonal and so there is no sufficient water.
- b) Water logging caused due to the heavy rain fall and imbalanced excessive immigration rote and affects germination in the sets.

2. Biological problems

- a) Red rat, smut grassy shoot and wilt are major diseases which are responsible for heavy use and quality in sugarcane.

3. Edifice problems

Soil fertility and productivity is continuously deteriorating biologically, chemically and physically with tremendous pressure on land. The size of heading is shrinking and

cropping intensity is increasing a soil fertility is also dwindling. This affected the production of sugarcane.

4. Technical problems

There is a lack of information regarding new varieties of sugarcane. Different varieties of sugarcane seeds are produced for different areas according to geographical factors. But no specific instructions are made available to the growers at the time of their real are. So this leads to defective choosing of sugarcane varieties.

5. Managerial problem

a) There is no timely availability of inputs such seeds, credit, farm power, implements, fertilizers, electricity, technical know - how, equipment, labour etc. The research in universities also cannot fulfil requirements of farmers due to their own limitations.

The farmer is poor and cannot possess all inputs and so he has to depend on hire system for cultivation services which are castle and unaffordable. This has brought down the production.

b) Poor and inadequate transfer of technology and lack of knowledge of modern techniques. Many agencies are involved in transfer of production technology e.g. agricultural universities, Agricultural department, zella parishads etc. But they lack uniformly in communicating the technology which leads to dconfusion in the minds of farmers and again the transfer is very slow. The farmer is also poor and ignorant and does not accept modem techniques.

6. Infrastructural problems

a) The sugarcane has to be transported immediately to factories, but most villages lack transport facilities like roads and thus the cane goes waste with much delay. Again, the farmer is poor and cannot afford quick means of transport.

b) There is imbalanced growth of sugar industries. Many industries are situated where sugarcane growing area is inadequate and many sugarcane growing areas do not have industries.

7. Higher cost of production

The cost of production is very high. Survey reveals that the cost varies from Rs. 10,000 to Rs. 13,000 per cane. The supervision charges fixed capital cost and its interest are not taken into account. This shows that farmers income is less.

8. Non - remunerative sugarcane price

Farmers receive quite low price as compared to costly, production. The profit margin is quite less to compared to short duration irrigated cash crops like vegetables, Cotton and fruits.

9. Government policies

Government policies regarding cane price incentives, incentives during shortage of production, export and import and import of sugar, controlled releases of sugar for distribution like in wages has an effect on profitability of sugar industry which in turn has impact on sugarcane price to farmer, many times it delays payment up setting the financial planning farmer to increase in his debt burden.

10. Labor problems

Absence of adequate number of trained labours for cane harvest is an important block in the harvest management program. Labor shortages are felt in several areas due to labour diversion to other crops, industrial work, construction work, etc, particularly near the urban centres. Arrangements must be made to get the labourers in required number to harvest the required quantity of cane every day. A healthy crop devoid of dash, properly earthed up, non - ledged with high tonnage will attract labourers since their turn out and earning will be more. Because now-a-days labour wages are paid on tonnage - based contract, particularly in the contract labour gangs are brought from far off places. Continuous work should be provided for them for proper development. Laborers should be given reasonable incentives which may include to and FRO- transport charges, medical benefits, accident benefits, provision of drinking water near the harvesting sites, etc. A higher teenager on tractor would further help. The waiting time should be minimized. Besides, the payments should be made to the labourers directly by the factories on weekly basis with the consent of the growers.

Labor shortages are going to be the common future in the decades to come. Therefore, mechanization of sugarcane harvesting will be suitable. Harvesting machine can harvest about 2 hectare per day. The machine may be tried by various factories to suit individual situations.

11. Post-harvest deterioration problem:

Post-harvest deterioration of cane occurs mainly due to delay in crushing of the harvested canes. The delay could be either in transporting or may even be in the yard. Post-harvest deterioration is highly influenced by several factors, viz, variety, maturity level of the crop, weather conditions, etc, apart from losses in cane weight and score deteriorated cane adds to reduced juice extraction. There will be problem of purification and filtration. In addition, dextrin formation is an important problem in the case of canes. It affects crystallization, A destine level of above 500 PPM. Results in the formation of needle shaped sugar crystals with difficulties in the separation of molasses.

12. Contingency Plan

Breakdown of sugarcane supply system can occur due to several reasons like problem of labour deployment, road collapse, accident, rains or any other social problems. Under such circumstances, the factory should have alternative sources of cane to make up the shortfall either from its own reserve area or from the neighbouring areas add to overcome the transport problems such arrangements are necessary. Sometimes, mill stoppage may occur due to some unexpected break down in the factory there, again contingency plan to divert the harvest cane to neighbouring mills, (in case such stoppages are more than 48 hours) is necessary.

13. Effective Communication

There should be an effective communication system to coordinate the harvest management activities. Wireless system is useful in many factories. At least all the cane sectional offices must be linked to the control office through telephones.

14. Mono cropping problem

Growing cane after cane is yet another important cause for verified decline. Mono cropping also leads to the build-up of diseases and pests causing vertical decline. In many

areas where decline in cane yield potential is observed mono cropping with multiple radioing practices is prevalent. E.g, in Khanapur taluka, due mono cropping sugarcane yield has come down only 18 to 22 tones. Thus, the sugarcane cultivation has many problems at every level from seeds to market.

Yet it holds an important position in the district in cropping pattern and agricultural scenario.

Objectives of study

1. The main objective of this paper is to identify various problems of sugarcane cultivation in M. K. Hubballi, Belgaum district, Karnataka state.
2. This study aims to determine the factors considered by the industry for sugarcane production.

NEED FOR STUDY

It is a well-known fact that a large proportion of the population in M. K. Hubballi, Belgaum district, Karnataka state consumes sugar in one form or another. This industry is considered one of the most important agro-based industries in our economy. In this regard, the problems of the sugarcane industry in M. K. Hubballi, Belgaum district, Karnataka state need to be addressed.

METHODOLOGY

This research article is a significant study where the main source of data collection is secondary data. The statistical data related to the study has been collected from UNCTAD Statistical Yearbook and UNCOMTRADE. Secondary data has been collected from books, journals, magazines, newspapers and relevant websites. The primary data collected is used to conduct the analysis. The analysis is carried out using the tools applicable to this study. Based on the analysis, the findings are reported and necessary suggestions are noted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sugar industry in M. K. Hubballi, Belgaum district, Karnataka state consists of three major components, namely sugarcane growers, sugar manufacturers and consumers. Sugarcane growers and sugar manufacturers form the main pressure group. The government looks after the interests of consumers through various rules and regulations.

Generally, it is seen that the sugar industry is mostly affected by overproduction or underproduction. Similarly, the sugar industry in the state of Karnataka is facing some problems that need to be reviewed from various perspectives, which are explained below.

❖ **Low Sugar Yield Sugarcane**

Sugar production depends on the quality and quantity of sugarcane available to the sugar factories. Therefore, the supply of sufficient quantity of good quality sugarcane at economical prices is very important. The problem of low sugarcane yield is due to our old farming methods, unavailability of suitable varieties, improper application of chemical fertilizers, manures, pesticides, lack of adequate irrigation facilities and unavailability of disease-free sugarcane seeds.

❖ **Chronic Instability**

This is one of the serious problems facing the sugar industry. There has been expansion and contraction in sugarcane production in a short period of time, resulting in wide fluctuations in sugarcane prices, which has led to difficulties on the part of producers. This chronic instability is due to both natural and man-made causes.

❖ **Low sugarcane price**

A sugar mill in Karnataka used to pay sugarcane prices based on their technical and economic performance or the weight of the sugarcane, but this does not give any incentive to the growers to grow better varieties of sugarcane with higher recovery. This system of paying sugarcane price is discouraging the growers who grow better quality sugarcane. They get the same as the growers who grow lower quality sugarcane.

❖ **Harvesting and transportation problem**

Some sugar factories are facing harvesting problem due to non-availability of labour during the season, but sugar industries have faced some problems while transporting sugarcane from the fields to the factory gates. Especially during the harvesting season, there is a shortage of labour force. Many labour contractors earn more money by supplying labour required for harvesting and transportation of sugarcane. The agreements entered into between the factories and the labour contractors are violated several times in order to get higher commission from the contractors. In such cases, the smooth functioning of the

sugar factories has been adversely affected due to distorted harvesting and transportation of sugarcane.

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❖ **Delay in payment of sugarcane price**

Since the 1981-82 season, the sugar industry has been facing liquidity problems arising from the existing huge sugar stocks. Since commercial banks only partially met the industry's funding requirement to support such huge stocks, the liquidity position of the industry was under considerable stress. This has led to a sharp rise in the amount of dues to be paid to the growers.

❖ **Small and uneconomical size of sugar plants**

Uneconomical size of the plant and obsolescence of plant and machinery are some of the problems of the sugar industries. The technologies currently adopted in many sugar factories are outdated because these plants were established long ago. The current sugar factories fall into the following age groups: 3 factories up to 5 years; 12 factories between 6 and 15 years, 11 factories between 16 and 25 years, 7 factories between 26 and 35 years and more than 35 years. 22 factories. As can be observed from the above, practically half of the sugar factories are more than 25 years old. The physical condition of these factories is very poor, resulting in high idle time and loss of capacity.

❖ **Slow technology transfer**

Modern farming practices, improved sugarcane varieties and conservation measures developed through sustained efforts of research and experimental stations for specific areas and conditions take a long time to reach sugarcane growers. Extension services that transmit the latest developments from laboratories to the field are considerably poor and inadequate. Slow technology transfer prevents growers from deriving maximum benefit from the research and experiments carried out. Lack of direct contact between sugar factories and sugarcane growers is another major factor adversely affecting development activities.

❖ **Under the utilization of by-products,**

The optimal development of any industry is usually judged by the efficiency of civilization of its by-products (biogases, molasses and press-mud), it is very sad to note that the sugar industry in the state has not paid much attention to the utilization of by-products in a good way.

SUGGESTIONS

The suggestions given here are intended to place the sugar industry on a stable footing, so that the sugar industry can grow faster than it is currently and be able to face future challenges with confidence.

- The area under sugarcane cultivation should be regulated to meet the needs of the sugar cooperatives. Sugarcane growers should be educated to enhance their knowledge of sugarcane cultivation in modern ways.
- A sound policy should be formulated to safeguard overall efficiency in sugarcane cultivation and stability in the sugar industry. Sugarcane prices should be fixed taking into account the cost of production of sugarcane, the profit to the growers from alternative crops and the general trend in prices of agricultural commodities.
- To overcome the problem of harvesting and transportation, the factories should adopt a proper varietal mix of early, medium and late ripening varieties. This will, to some extent, enable them to harvest sugarcane in the months of October/November when the labourers are relatively free. There should be a direct link between the farmers and the factories, so that higher yields can be obtained.

- The cost of running the plant and over-transporting of sugarcane during crushing season and off-season should be reduced by planning and scheduling the work, fixing standards for each cost centre.
- Efforts should be made to increase the capacity of these sugar factories by expanding them or merging small units into larger units, so that they can be made economically viable.

There is an urgent need to encourage investment in expansion and modernization of existing sugar factories instead of making fresh investments in new sugar factories. Therefore, the licensing policy regarding the sugar industry should be modified accordingly.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The sugar industry in M. K. Hubballi, Belgaum district of Karnataka state has good prospects in the current and coming years. The source of sugar is sugarcane, which is cultivated by the growers with immense effort. The problems and concerns affecting the sugarcane industry can be understood as follows: lack of capital, lack of availability of skilled labor, increasing input and transportation costs, etc. The need of the day is to pay attention to the problems of the sugarcane industries and provide support, if needed, especially to small growers and industries.

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